

FORMING OF ALIGNED FIBER COMPOSITES; GEOMETRY AND EXPERIMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Differential geometry theory is used to show how an ideal aligned fiber composite (incompressible, inextensible fibers, constant uniform spacing between fibers) must be deformed in order to make a part of complex curvature. Three fundamental results are given; the first two relate the required shears to the fiber curvatures (normal and geodesic), and the third, called the Gauss-Bonnet theorem, relates the shears to the Gaussian curvature of the part and the fiber orientation. Experimental results for room temperature diaphragm forming of thermoset prepregs are given, and it is shown how these results can be simplified using differential geometry theory.

1. INTRODUCTION

During processing, incompressible aligned fiber composites with inextensible fibers, can be deformed with only two modes; longitudinal shear and transverse shear. Of these two, the ability to conform to a complex shape is governed almost solely by longitudinal shear. For thin sheets and the material coordinate system shown in Fig. 1, there are two longitudinal shears; Γ_{13} is the through-the-thickness component, and Γ_{12} is the in-plane component. These special volume conserving shears, which are illustrated in Fig. 2, are defined as,

$$\Gamma_{ij} = \frac{\delta_i}{h_j}. \quad (1)$$

In this paper we will outline how these shears are related to the fiber curvatures and part curvatures for the forming of constant thickness ($\Gamma_{23} = \Gamma_{32} = 0$) aligned fiber sheets into any arbitrary topologically equivalent complex shape. Furthermore, for a given material and process, we will show from experiments that the required shear is a critical measure of the ability of the composite to conform to a given shape.

Fig.1 Material Coordinate System

Fig.2 Large Strain Shear

2. DIFFERENTIAL GEOMETRY THEORY

To make a complex composite part, the forming operation must curve the fibers somehow to conform to the shape. In general the curvature of a single fiber may be described by a vector. This vector can be obtained from a knowledge of the fiber path. For example, if we represent the fiber path with a vector \hat{x} , and use the arc length "s" as a parameter, then the fiber path can be given as,

$$\hat{x} = \hat{x}(s). \tag{2}$$

The curvature vector \hat{k} can be obtained from eq. 2 as,

$$\hat{k} = \frac{d^2 \hat{x}}{ds^2} = \kappa \hat{n}. \tag{3}$$

In eq. 3 the magnitude of the curvature is κ and its direction is \hat{n} , it can be shown that \hat{n} is normal to the fiber.

The actual type of deformation required of the composite depends upon the relationship between the fiber curvature to the part surface. In Fig. 3 is shown a surface and a fiber on it. The vector \hat{N} is normal to the surface at our point of interest and \hat{u} lies in the tangent plane for the surface and is perpendicular to the fiber. Writing the fiber curvature vector in terms of these two orthogonal directions gives,

$$\hat{k} = \kappa_n \hat{N} + \kappa_g \hat{u}. \tag{4}$$

The two curvature components in eq. 4 are the normal curvature κ_n and the geodesic curvature κ_g . To form an aligned fiber composite to a complex shape the two shears (in-plane and through-the-thickness) are directly related to these curvature components. For example, using our definition given in eq. (1) it can be shown that the in-plane shear for fiber, Γ_{12} , can be written as [1, 2, 3].

$$\Gamma_{12} = \int_0^L k_g(s) ds + \Gamma_{12(0)}. \tag{5}$$

Fig.3 Fiber on a curved surface

The constant $\Gamma_{12(0)}$ allows for a constant shear along the entire length of the fiber. Similarly, the through-the-thickness shear for a fiber can be written as

$$\Gamma_{13} = \int_0^L k_n(s) ds + \Gamma_{13(0)}. \quad (6)$$

These two relationships are fundamental to understanding the shear deformation of aligned fiber composites. They can be further related to the complex curvature of the part by the application of an important theorem of differential geometry known as the Gauss-Bonnet theorem [4]. It can be developed as follows: since both eq. (5) and (6) are line integrals, if performed around a closed, piecewise smooth curve c , their result can be related to the nature of the enclosed region, of area A , by the application of Green's theorem. The result from integrating in the plane of the composite is,

$$\int_c \kappa_g ds + \int_A K dA = 2\pi - \sum \theta_i. \quad (7)$$

Here, K is the "Gaussian curvature", which is the product of the two principal curvatures for the surface at a point. The angles θ_i are defined in the accompanying Fig.

4. Eq. (7) is also a fundamental equation for understanding the shear deformation of aligned fiber composites, since it relates shear to the shape of the part and the fiber orientation. By judicious application of this theorem, one can obtain some very useful results for understanding the deformation of aligned fiber composites. We have worked out several important examples including hemispheres, cones, and contoured channels [2,3].

3. EXPERIMENTS

A number of experiments have been carried out using drape forming [2,3] and diaphragm forming [7] techniques with AS-4 3501-6 prepreg at or near room temperature. Analysis of the results can be significantly aided using the differential geometry theory outlined in the previous section. This theory allows the in-plane shear

Fig.4 Illustration of Gauss-Bonnet theorem

necessary to form a part to be related to its geometry. Fig.5 shows the fiber patterns and shear distributions for the part shapes studied in this work. The figure shows that though the maximum shear required to form both boxes and hemispheres is π , the shear distributions are markedly different. The build up of shear on a hemisphere is gradual whereas on the boxes it occurs in a step or as a series of steps. This critical difference in shear distributions shows why it is much more difficult to form a box than a hemisphere. Note that when constructing the "ideal" fiber maps on complex surfaces one has two independent variables. The first is the placement of a single fiber. This will determine the placement of all other fibers and their total shear. The second independent variable is the "clamp line" which determines how the shear is distributed over the length of the fiber. For example, on the hemisphere, the midpoint of each fiber could be fixed relative to adjacent fibers and shear constrained to develop equally on either side of the midpoint. Alternatively, all fibers could be fixed relative to one another along one edge, with each fiber subsequently going through the whole shear along its entire length.

4.0 EXPERIMENTAL APPARATUS

All experiments were carried out using the diaphragm forming apparatus shown in Fig. 6. It consists of a tool platform, of adjustable height, surrounded by a 45 cm diameter transparent polycarbonate tube. The base is aluminum while the top cover consists of a polycarbonate sheet strengthened by aluminum sheet and mild steel "L" section reinforcing bars. The top sheet of aluminum contains a viewing window. Forming experiments were carried out on laminated unidirectional prepreg consisting of Hercules AS-4 high strength graphite fibers in 3501-6 epoxy. In most experiments, two ply $0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminates were formed at room temperature, though other geometries and forming temperatures were also used. Transparent silicone rubber diaphragms of different stiffnesses were used, in order to investigate the effect of diaphragm properties on the quality of formed parts. The forming sequence was as follows. Net shape

Fig.5 Fiber patterns and shear distributions for boxes and hemispheres

preforms (determined by back calculating from the ideal fiber pattern) were cut and laminated as desired. The preforms were placed between the silicone rubber diaphragms, oriented as necessary relative to the tool, and the assembly bolted together. Lubrication between diaphragms and preform was achieved with petroleum gel. Forming experiments were carried out using positive pressures of between 27.5 and 55 kPa. The rate of application of pressure was controlled using a manually adjusted valve and pressure gauge. Upon completion of forming, the part could be examined more closely by removing the top diaphragm, the bottom diaphragm being held in place by the application of vacuum from beneath. A relaxation time of up to an hour was allowed to elapse before removing the part from the tool and taking measurements.

5. RESULTS

The primary modes necessary to form complex shapes from aligned fiber composites are in-plane shear and interply shear. However, in practical forming operations, undesirable deformation modes such as fiber buckling, laminate wrinkling, tow splitting and fiber spreading frequently occur, and for the most part, are more easily induced than in-plane shear. Diaphragm forming is seen as a process of particular promise as it supplies the normal support necessary to suppress out-of-plane deformation modes such as buckling and laminate wrinkling. In the present study the effects of a number of process parameters on the quality of diaphragm formed parts was investigated. Particular focus was applied to explaining effects due to part geometry, though forming rate and temperature effects were studied.

Fig. 7 shows a 15 cm. diameter hemisphere formed in approx. 10 mins. from a 2 ply preform of $0^\circ/90^\circ$ lay up geometry. The picture shows some common forms of defects. Extensive fiber buckling is seen over a large area of the part accompanied by tow splitting

Fig.6 Diaphragm forming apparatus

Fig. 7 ($0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$) hemisphere diaphragm formed over 10 min. time period

It is noticeable that the buckles occur predominantly on the lower sides of the tows. Thus upon splitting apart, the tows appear to behave as beams, with a tensile side, and a compressive side where buckling occurs. Hemispheres ranging in size from 1.9 cm to 15 cm in diameter were formed, and it was noted that the tendency toward buckling scaled with part size, the smallest hemispheres being essentially free of buckles. In order to avoid buckling, shears generated in the center of the part must be allowed to propagate out to the fiber ends, in a manner described by shear slip theory [3,6]. Fiber stress increases proportionately with increasing part size (effective fiber length) and similarly the tendency toward buckling. Further experiments were carried out where the rate of deformation was varied by up to 1.5 orders of magnitude. Fig. 8 shows a hemisphere formed over a 5 hour period and the degree of fiber buckling is noticeably lower than on the more rapidly formed part. Earlier work has shown that the volume fraction of buckled fibers increases with deformation rate in parts formed by simple bending [5]. Shear slip theory predicts that the fiber stress increases with shear rate, thus the results presented may be explained.

Though reducing the forming rate appears to reduce the degree of buckling, it also gives rise to other forms of failure. As can be seen in Fig. 8, fiber spreading and tow splitting are serious problems and sections of the laminate have been torn off, in the transverse direction. This is believed to be caused by interaction between the laminate and the diaphragm, where the lubricant was effectively squeezed out, permitting contact and adhesion. This is a problem that also occurs in production scale diaphragm forming

Fig.8 (0/90) hemisphere formed over a 5 hour time period

Fig.9 ($\pm 45^\circ$) box showing deviation from ideal fiber paths

operations, and may limit the extent to which deformation rate reduction can be used to suppress buckling. Reducing viscosity by increasing processing temperature is a strategy that can also be employed. But too high a processing temperature leads to failures similar to that shown in Fig. 8.

In many of the parts formed by this process the fiber paths deviated significantly from ideality and this is shown clearly in Fig. 7, and also in Fig. 9 where a box formed with fiber orientation of $\pm 45^\circ$ is shown. On an "ideal" hemisphere the fibers at the end of the part should go through π shear, essentially almost folding back on themselves. In actuality this is not observed on the actual parts. On an ideal $\pm 45^\circ$ box the κ_g should be concentrated along a line oriented at 22.5° to the top face, as shown in Fig. 5 and highlighted by the white line in Fig. 9. Though the fibers follow close to ideal paths near the leftmost edge, deviation increases progressively with increasing horizontal distance toward the right. This misalignment was evaluated by measuring the distance between ideal and the actual fiber paths at the edge of the part, referenced to some central fiber which may be thought of as an "initially placed" fiber. On a hemisphere the reference is the central fiber; on a $\pm 45^\circ$ box it is the diagonal fiber, and on a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ box it is the top fiber closest to the edge. The misalignment was measured for hemispheres ranging in diameter from 1.9 cm to 15 cm, and 7.5 cm square boxes with fiber orientation of $0^\circ/90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$. In Fig. 10 misalignment is shown to correlate with the integral of shear in the transverse direction up to the point of measurement. Thus the experimental data appears to fit the relation,

Fig.10 Experimental forming data for boxes and hemispheres

$$\Delta m = C_{p,m} \int_0^{s_n} \Gamma_{12} ds_n \quad (8)$$

where $C_{p,m}$ is a constant, dependent on the chosen process and material system. This empirical relationship strongly suggests the importance of the shear distribution in making arbitrary complex shaped parts with ideal fiber placement and uniform thickness.

6. DISCUSSION

The purpose of this work is to outline how differential geometry theory can be used to understand the formation of complex shaped composite parts. We have shown how the in-plane shear required to form a part is dependant only on; 1) the placement of the first fiber, 2) the complex curvature of the part, and 3) the clamp line. How a particular process controls these variables depends upon the details of the process. However the proposal which we are making here, is that the relative success of the process to make good parts of different geometries depends on the nature of the required in-plane shear. In the case of fiber placement and thickness uniformity, this was shown in Fig.10, for the case of buckling, the relevant parameter is $d\Gamma/dt$

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REFERENCES

1. T.G. Gutowski, A. Tam, G. Dillon, & S. Stoller, "Forming Aligned Fiber Composites into Complex Shapes", *CIRP Annals*, Vol. 40, No. 1, 1991.
2. A.S. Tam and T.G. Gutowski, "The Kinematics of Forming Ideal Aligned Fiber Composites", *Composites Manufacturing*, Vol.1, No.4, Dec. 1990.
3. A.S. Tam, "A Deformation Model for the Forming of Aligned Fiber Composites", Ph.D. Thesis, Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, June 1990.
4. D.J. Struik, Lectures in Classical Differential Geometry, Dover Publications Inc., New York, 1988.
5. W.E. Soll and T.G. Gutowski, "Forming Thermoplastic Composite Parts", *Proceedings of the 33rd International SAMPE Symposium*, Anaheim , CA, March 1988.
6. A.S. Tam and T.G. Gutowski, "Ply-Slip During the Forming of Thermoplastic Composite Parts", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 23, June 1989.
7. S. Stoller, "Forming Limits of Advanced Composite Materials" S.M. Thesis, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Massachusetts Institute of Technology., to be submitted June 1991.